

Real-Time Fuel-Optimal Guidance Using Deep Neural Networks and Differential Algebra

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This work presents a method to compute continuous low-thrust fuel-optimal guidance updates on board a spacecraft using a combination of deep learning and differential algebraic techniques. In order to create the large datasets necessary to train neural networks, we also propose a new method using polynomial maps, which provide fuel-optimal guidance updates for any state deviation from a nominal. Constructing the map at the initial time allows the generation of an arbitrarily high number of optimal trajectories for the database via the simple evaluation of polynomials. A trained deep neural network is then capable of providing continuous guidance updates, for which an interplanetary transfer scenario from Earth to Psyche is chosen for evaluation of the guidance schemes performance. As a neural network cannot generalise the highly complex mapping between state and optimal control policy perfectly, one expects some error in the policy. For sensitive dynamical systems and large flight times, this error may be unsuitable for the mission. We therefore further utilise differential algebraic techniques to refine the output of the neural network into highly accurate fuel-optimal guidance updates via a lightweight and iterative-less mapping procedure, suitable for onboard implementation.

1 Introduction

Over recent years the use of deep neural networks (DNNs) to autonomously control various systems has gained considerable traction, with applications to robotics, drones, aircraft, and more recently spacecraft [1–7]. Such a network is tasked with learning the mapping between the state and optimal control policy, which in general is a highly complex relationship and except in the most simplest of systems a perfect generalisation does not exist. Therefore, the network produces a best fit of such a mapping, based on some loss function, and there will exist some error between the predicted and optimal control policy. Producing the best mapping is then the main goal of DNN-guidance research, and the performance is often assessed based

on such an error. While DNNs that replicate the thrust direction and throttle magnitude (as in the previously referenced works) show resilience to this error, trajectories controlled via the indirect method of optimal control theory are highly sensitive to errors in the costate, hence even a highly sophisticated DNN may not be able to replicate the optimal costates to the required accuracy for immediate application to the mission, as explored in recent research [8]. For these reasons, applications of costate learning have thus far mostly been limited to providing better initial guesses for faster convergence of the indirect problem for use in database generation [6, 7]. However in such cases, it may be possible to implement post-processing to refine the inaccurate output costates of the DNN into the accurate optimal policies which satisfy mission constraints.

In this work we investigate the use of a DNN to learn the optimal costates and time of flights for autonomous fuel-optimal guidance, and present a refinement method using differential algebra (DA) techniques. To address the challenges of dataset generation, we also propose an efficient method utilising polynomial maps to rapidly generate an arbitrarily high number of fuel-optimal trajectories. This ultimately reduces the problem of solving an excessively large number of optimal control problems (OCPs) to solving a minor subset, after which any optimal trajectory in the defined state-space can be described based on this subset. DA then provides the tools necessary to expand trajectories obtained from the DNN. Utilising algorithms for polynomial composition and inversion, the required updates to the DNN costate may be found to satisfy the optimality conditions, thus providing the fuel-optimal trajectory. The DA algorithm is iterative-less and lightweight, and additionally is capable of handling varying control sequences. The performance of the entire guidance scheme, which includes both DNN and refinement, is assessed in an interplanetary transfer from Earth to the asteroid (16) Psyche.

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2 Free-Time Fuel-Optimal Guidance

2.1 Optimal Control Problem

The free-time fuel-optimal control problem for a low-thrust rendezvous with Psyche is defined as finding the optimal control and time-of-flight such that the fuel consumption is minimised over a trajectory starting from some state $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^7$ which coincides with Earth at the initial time, evolves according to the dynamics \dot{x} , and terminates at Psyche. In contrast to the fixed-time problem, allowing the final time to be free provides increased flexibility. This can result in more efficient trajectories that avoid unnecessary acceleration and deceleration phases otherwise required to meet the fixed time constraint. However, defining a cost function that is solely a function of the fuel consumption would be ill-defined, as if one allows the flight time $\rightarrow \infty$ then the propellant usage $\rightarrow 0$, due to the ability to coast for vast periods of time. Thus, an additional term based on a reference time-of-flight $t^* = 1065$ days is introduced for which a cost is incurred should the time-of-flight differ significantly from this reference, thereby allowing a reasonable amount of variation. This work employs the indirect method of optimal control theory which, to summarise, results in the introduction of a costate $\lambda(t) \in \mathbb{R}^7$ and associated dynamics $\dot{\lambda}$, as well as a set of optimality conditions which must be satisfied at a terminal time t_f to be determined. λ ultimately defines the optimal control direction and throttle magnitude $u \in [0, 1]$, via Primer vector theory [9] and Pontryagin's maximum principle respectively. Crucially, once the optimal λ and t_f are found, propagating the state and costate with the associated \dot{x} and $\dot{\lambda}$ provides the entire optimal trajectory until t_f . In the case of fuel-optimal problems, the throttle magnitude only takes the extremal values of either 0 or 1, resulting in a discontinuous control commonly referred to as 'bang-bang'. The problem is thus reduced to a two-point boundary value problem (TPBVP), for which shooting methods are typically used to find the initial λ and t_f which results in a trajectory that satisfies all the optimality conditions.

Discontinuous controls notoriously cause problems for solving algorithms, resulting in techniques such as homotopy methods being employed to remedy convergence issues. One such method is to substitute the bang-bang control with a smooth control [10, 11], which is continuously differentiable, of the form

$$u_s = \frac{1}{1 + e^{\epsilon \rho}} \quad (1)$$

where $\rho(x, \lambda, t)$ is the switching function, derived

during the indirect method. The smoothness of the control is adjusted with the parameter ϵ , for which as $\epsilon \rightarrow \infty$ the control becomes equivalent to the optimal bang-bang control. This control is partially utilised in this work, for which $\epsilon = 1000$ is used and replicated the bang-bang control closely whilst removing the discontinuities. In fact, as both \dot{x} and $\dot{\lambda}$ are functions of the control, bang-bang controls results in discontinuous x and λ profiles over the trajectories. Discontinuities in the dataset can result in problems in the policy learning, therefore trajectories based on u_s should result in improved learning. Thus, the databases introduced in the following section are all based on trajectories using u_s .

2.2 Database Generation

The proposed supervised learning requires a database of state and time $[x, t]$ and optimal costate and time-of-flight $[\lambda, t_f]$ pairs. As this requires optimal trajectories, one needs to solve many TPBVPs between varying boundary states to generate a distribution of data points over the entire potential state space. Unfortunately, solving the TPBVP is often a slow process, which suffers from convergence issues without the availability of a good initial guess. In [6], this is remedied by using a DNN trained on an initial dataset to provide better initial guesses for further solutions to the OCP, speeding up sample generation to improve the dataset size for further training, albeit still requiring an OCP-solver for each trajectory. In [1], a new methodology called backward generation of optimal examples was proposed, whereby solving a single nominal trajectory and then perturbing the final costate such that the optimality conditions were still satisfied yielded a new optimal trajectory which could then be back-propagated and sampled accordingly. The authors then implemented this method to generate extensive databases in a rapid and efficient manner. Although the state-space of the generated trajectories cannot be inherently controlled, using small perturbations results in trajectories that are close to the nominal.

In this work, we present an alternative method using polynomial maps to efficiently and rapidly generate a database in which an even distribution of trajectories can be guaranteed, as well as the ability to bound the state-space of the trajectories, ensuring each data point is within a desired domain of operation and avoiding outliers which could otherwise be detrimental to the learning process. A polynomial map is created at the initial time, consisting of a set of patches that span a specified uncertainty domain, with each patch providing a set of high-order guidance polynomials for which the truncation error does

Figure 1: Visualisation of the generated training database.

not exceed a specified tolerance. For any deviation from the nominal, the polynomial map can be evaluated and guidance updates are readily provided (i.e., updates to λ and t_f) which are to a specified accuracy. During the generation of such a map, each patch requires the solving of a single optimal trajectory, starting at the centre of the patch and satisfying the rendezvous conditions, and once expanded using Taylor polynomials, any trajectory in that patch can be described based on the single solved trajectory. For the Earth-Psyche scenario, this reduced the problem to finding a set of just 32 trajectories. The creation of the polynomial map took just 142 seconds, carried out on an Intel i7-12700 CPU running at 2.1GHz with parallel computation enabled on 12 logical cores. Testing 1×10^6 evaluations of the polynomials maps, the average evaluation time was 27.8 microseconds, demonstrating that the generation of trajectories is both efficiency and rapid.

Trajectories are rapidly generated from the aforementioned polynomial map, each split into k equal segments over their corresponding time of flight. A uniform distribution is then used to sample a random state from within each segment, resulting in an evenly distributed dataset without bias otherwise caused by sampling at set intervals. Three datasets are created: a training set $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$ with $k = 500$ consisting of 10,000,000 samples which is visualised in Figure 1; a validation set \mathcal{D}_{val} with $k = 100$ consisting of 100,000 samples; and a test set $\mathcal{D}_{\text{test}}$ with $k = 1$ consisting of 1000 samples.

2.3 Deep Neural Network

A DNN is trained on $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$. Standardisation is performed on the dataset prior to training, such that the resulting distribution for each item in the dataset has a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. The goal is to learn the mapping $[x, t] \mapsto [\lambda, t_f]$. The network consists of seven hidden layers, each with 256 neurons per layer. A study of the mostly commonly used activation layers revealed that ReLU produced the best policy learning and was subsequently selected for the final network. Following discoveries made in [1],

Kaiming normal initialisation was implemented for the weights. A study of optimisers also revealed that the AdamW optimiser without AMSgrad produced the best results. The loss function is the mean squared error between the predicted $[\lambda, t_f]$ and corresponding optimal values. The number of epochs was set to 200, and the batch size to 1000. The initial learning rate was set to 1×10^{-3} , and was decreased by a factor of 0.6 should the loss calculated on \mathcal{D}_{val} not improve by 1% over 10 epochs.

2.4 Differential Algebraic Refinement

Previous research indicates that DNNs for costate replication often exhibit poor performance in comparison to DNNs used to replicate the control direction and magnitude policies directly [6–8]. During our investigations, it was observed that small errors in the predicted λ result in large state errors at the final time. Indeed, as the DNNs cannot learn the optimal λ and t_f with absolute accuracy, one should expect small errors in the policy imitation. Consequently, unsatisfactorily large errors in the terminal state were observed when using the DNNs alone to control the spacecraft.

We therefore present a method of refining the inaccurate outputs of the DNN into accurate optimal updates via DA. The DNN provides a close initial guess of the optimal λ and t_f which may be expanded using DA techniques, and by enforcing the set of optimality conditions the optimal updates may be readily obtained. The DA refinement algorithm consists of three steps:

1. Refinement of the resulting trajectory from the DNN with the smoothed control u_s from Equation (1). Obtaining this intermediate trajectory has important consequences for the next step.
2. Detection of the switching times t_s and thrust sequence on the trajectory from the previous step. As this trajectory uses a smoothed approximation of the optimal bang-bang control, the thrust sequence this trajectory exhibits when propagated with the bang-bang control is identical to the optimal one. The detected t_s provide close initial guesses of the optimal ones. The detection is carried out within an efficient Runge-Kutta-7-8 integrator, which due to being variable step results in an over-stepping of the true switching times. Therefore the obtained t_s are refined using DA for highly accurate detection.
3. Mapping λ , t_f , and t_s into the corresponding optimal values based on the bang-bang control. As the control is now the optimal form instead of the approximation u_s , and the mapping enforces the optimality conditions of the TPBVP, the resulting trajectory is fuel-optimal.

Figure 2: Rendezvous residuals for: nominal only, DNN only, nominal + DA refinement, and DNN + DA refinement.

Each of the DA algorithms listed above are lightweight and entirely iterative-less, suitable for real-time onboard application. In this work we perform 2nd order refinements, which was found to balance computational time and accuracy well.

3 Results

For comparison, the performance of trajectories by using: nominal costate only (i.e., continuing as if flying on the original nominal trajectory) vs. DNN only vs. nominal + refinement vs. DNN + refinement, is assessed on \mathcal{D}_{test} . The resulting position residual distributions are shown in Figure 2 and reported in the top part of Table 1. As expected, the unguided trajectories using only the nominal costates produce extremely large final state residuals. The use of the DNN for guidance reduces these residuals by 2 orders of magnitude. Despite this reduction, the residuals are still unacceptable for the mission. The refinement of the nominal costates displays acceptable residuals to 1σ . These correspond to test states that have not deviated too far from the nominal and consequently the nominal costate is an adequately close guess to the

Figure 3: Illustration of nominal vs. DNN trajectories for refinement. The optimal solution lies solely within the convergence radius of the expanded DNN trajectory.

Test case	Position Residuals (km)		
	1σ	2σ	3σ
Nominal only	3.11×10^7	1.78×10^8	3.17×10^8
DNN only	4.12×10^5	3.73×10^6	1.14×10^7
Nominal + DA	0.00586	1.34×10^7	5.97×10^7
DNN + DA	2.71×10^{-5}	0.00649	8.8
\mathcal{D}_{test+}	0.00329	1.58	1.21×10^3
Thrust Err.	41	170	566
Navigation Err.	260	920	2.48×10^3

Table 1: Position residuals for all tests.

required optimal costate for the refinement process. However, the 2σ and 3σ residuals are found to be worse than solely using the DNN. As the DA refinement algorithm is based on local expansions of the flow, the resulting mapping possesses a convergence radius. When the spacecraft deviates too far from the nominal trajectory, and thus the nominal costates provide a bad initial guess and an inaccurate trajectory, the optimal solution is outside of the convergence radius of the polynomials, which is illustrated in Figure 3. Consequently, the mapping produces large errors due to the divergence of the polynomial approximation outside of the convergence radius. Only the DNN with refinement approach produces acceptable rendezvous tolerances for all test cases. This is due to the DNN reliably producing sufficiently close guesses of the optimal costate, such that the optimal solution always lies within the convergence radius of the corresponding expanded trajectories. Hence, for robust guidance, the combination of the DNN and DA refinement techniques are required.

The trained DNN and DA refinement algorithm is further assessed using three different simulations:

1. The guidance algorithm is assessed on a second test dataset \mathcal{D}_{test+} . Following the methodology outlined in Section 2.2, a second polynomial map is created with a domain size 10% larger than the original map. To create \mathcal{D}_{test+} , 1000 samples are taken from the additional domain compared to the original, therefore generating trajectories outside of the training domain. The aim of this test is to assess how well the guidance algorithm can perform outside of the training region.
2. A Monte Carlo simulation in which, starting on the nominal trajectory, randomised thrust direction errors affect the trajectory. 20 sets of errors equally affect the spacecraft between each guidance implementation. The elevation error is Gaussian with zero mean and $\sigma = 1^\circ$. The azimuth error is uniformly distributed between 0 and 360° .

Figure 4: Rendezvous residuals for tests 1 to 4 using DNN + DA guidance.

3. A Monte Carlo simulation in which, starting on the nominal trajectory, randomised navigation errors affect the trajectory. The errors are modelled by zero-mean Gaussian distributions, with $\sigma = 0.1$ km for each of the position coordinates and $\sigma = 0.05$ m/s for each of the velocity coordinates.

The simulated guidance frequency is set to 5 days, the objective being to optimally guide the spacecraft until 20 days before the target rendezvous time, allowing an approach-phase guidance to assume command for orbit insertion. Figure 4 displays the rendezvous position residuals for all tests, as well as the assessment on $\mathcal{D}_{\text{test}}$ for reference, and the statistics are reported in the latter part of Table 1, overall showing a highly successful guidance scheme. In the context of an interplanetary transfer, these residuals are small and plenty sufficient for the terminal-phase guidance to place the spacecraft into orbit. The increased fuel expenditure compared to the nominal for tests 2 and 3 was $3\sigma = +0.019\%$ and $3\sigma = +0.0074\%$ respectively, highlighting the fuel-optimality of the guidance scheme in the presence of errors.

4 Discussion

This work attempts to learn the optimal λ and t_f policies via deep learning. As mentioned, DNNs will not replicate these with absolute accuracy, and it was noted that small errors in these quantities correlate to large errors in the terminal state. One could alternatively switch to learning the optimal thrust direction and magnitude directly, which has been shown to display good performance when replicated with

DNNs [1–3, 12]. However the learning of the costate presents some advantages. Once the optimal λ and t_f are obtained, the optimal thrust direction and throttle magnitude are provided for the entire future trajectory. Whilst the guidance implementation would still be frequent to address perturbations, the key difference is that the costate also provides the control in between guidance implementations. In contrast, when directly replicating thrust direction and magnitude, these quantities remain fixed between guidance implementations, thus necessitating the high implementation frequency. Such high frequency may require significant power supply to continuously obtain the navigation measurements to evaluate the DNN. Thus costate learning may be able to reduce the strain on the onboard systems and power consumption.

Regarding the database generation technique, there are several notable benefits when using the polynomial maps for database generation. Firstly, there is a vast reduction in the number of TPBVPs to solve. Secondly, the generated trajectory envelope can be bounded via the specified initial domain. This can avoid generating trajectories that are outside of the anticipated domain of operation, which ideally would be discarded and computational time wasted, or at worst would impact the learning process, as the DNN would be required to learn a larger state-space than necessary. Moreover, such highly deviated trajectories can negatively affect the data standardisation process typically performed before training. Finally, an even distribution of trajectories in the state-space can be guaranteed, avoiding areas of sparse data and thus an under representation during the training process which could have adverse affects on the DNN predictions in these areas.

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